

HYDROXYFLUOBERYLLATES. PART III. HYDROXYFLUOBERYLLATES OF COPPER, ZINC, CADMIUM, NICKEL, MANGANESE, MAGNESIUM, COBALT AND IRON

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The hydroxyfluoberyllate of copper, magnesium, zinc, cadmium, manganese, iron, cobalt and nickel have been prepared and their properties have been described. The compounds crystallise with varying number of water molecules, e.g. 5, 4, 3, 2 and 1. The chemical composition of these compounds is analogous with the corresponding sulphates. The solubilities of these salts are, however, by far greater than the corresponding sulphate or fluoberyllate. Some of these compounds are moreover deliquescent in nature. Nickel hydroxyfluoberyllate hexahydrate has been proved to be isomorphous with nickel sulphate hexahydrate.

Hydroxyfluoberyllates of the alkali metals and some insoluble or sparingly soluble hydroxyfluoberyllates have been described previously by the author (*this Journal*, 1955, 32, 241, 246). The hydroxyfluoberyllates of the copper-magnesium group of metals are now described. These hydroxyfluoberyllates are highly soluble in water and possess water of crystallisation. The isolation and chemical formulae of these salts prove further that the hydroxyfluoberyllate ion is a quite stable one under the normal conditions and exhibits strong resemblance with the sulphate group.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fluorine in these compounds was estimated as lead chlorofluoride or as calcium fluoride. The other constituents were determined by the standard methods.

Methods of Preparation.—Three general methods were followed for the preparation of these compounds.

(1). A weighed quantity of the carbonate or the freshly precipitated hydroxide of the metal was taken in a platinum basin and dissolved in the minimum quantity of 15% hydrofluoric acid. A slight excess of the equimolecular amount of freshly precipitated beryllium hydroxide was then added to it, and the basin heated on a water-bath; hydrofluoric acid (10%) was added to it little at a time. The addition of hydrofluoric acid was stopped when the solution became just turbid due to the presence of traces of undissolved beryllium hydroxide. The solution was filtered and the filtrate kept in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid at 25° to 35°.

(2). A saturated solution of the nitrite of the metal, obtained by the double decomposition between the sulphate of the metal and barium nitrite, was added to a saturated solution of ammonium hydroxyfluoberyllate. The solution was allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator at the ordinary temperature.

(3). To a concentrated solution of silver hydroxyfluoberyllate a saturated solution containing the requisite amount of the metallic chloride was added. The white

precipitate formed was filtered and the solution was allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator. The crystals obtained after a few days were washed with 60% alcohol and dried by pressing in the folds of a filter paper or in a desiccator.

The first method is by far the best and easiest one. The following compounds were isolated as a result of the present investigation.

Copper hydroxyfluoberyllate pentahydrate was obtained by the first method. The crystals obtained by the second method were always contaminated with some amount of basic salts. (Found: Cu, 26.85; F, 23.92; Be, 3.66. $\text{CuBeF}_3\text{OH}\cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 26.86; F, 24.11; Be, 3.81 per cent).

The transparent blue crystals are highly soluble in water and in 80% alcohol; in latter solvent copper fluoberyllate is practically insoluble. These crystals are perfectly stable. On long exposure to atmospheric conditions a greenish crust is formed due to the formation of the basic salts. When finely powdered crystals of pentahydrated copper hydroxyfluoberyllate are kept over sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator for weeks, they lose water to form a monohydrate. (Found: Loss in wt., 30.91%. $\text{CuBeF}_3\text{OH}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires loss in wt., 30.45%). At 100° copper hydroxyfluoberyllate becomes green, forming anhydrous salt.

Magnesium Hydroxyfluoberyllate Monohydrate.—The corresponding fluoberyllate salt is not definitely known. Recently, its existence has been suggested by Perfect (*Proc. Penn. Acad. Sci.*, 1952, 28, 54). The phase diagram study of the system $\text{BeF}_2\text{-MgF}$ could not reveal the existence of magnesium fluoberyllate (Venturello, *Atti Accad. Sci. Torino*, 1941, 61, 556). Hydroxyfluoride complexes are from certain viewpoints more stable than the corresponding fluoride complexes, and isolation of the monohydrated magnesium hydroxyfluoberyllate confirms the above view.

For the preparation of this salt the second method was applied. A few drops of amyl alcohol was, however, added in order to suppress the secondary dissociation. The resulting solution was allowed to concentrate slowly at a low temperature (below 10°). After a week it was filtered and to the filtrate was added an equal volume of alcohol. The solution, thus obtained, was again allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator inside a refrigerator. White microscopic crystals appeared after two days. (Found: Mg, 19.70; F, 45.49; Be, 6.92. $\text{MgBeF}_3\text{OH}\cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mg, 19.39; F, 45.45; Be, 7.19 per cent).

The substance on heating to 100° lost 14.28% of its weight. H_2O calculated for the monohydrated salt is 14.37%. The heptahydrated and the anhydrous salts could not be isolated. Magnesium hydroxyfluoberyllate is deliquescent in nature.

Zinc hydroxyfluoberyllate heptahydrate was prepared by the first method. The second method also furnished this product, but first two crops should be rejected in this case as they always contained some zinc ammonium hydroxyfluoberyllate as an impurity. (Found: Zn, 23.68; F, 20.92; Be, 3.12. $\text{ZnBeF}_3\text{OH}\cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 23.81; F, 20.76; Be, 3.28 per cent).

When this salt was heated to a constant weight at 50°, it changed to the hexahydrated salt. (Found: Loss in wt., 6.72%. $\text{ZnBeF}_3\text{OH}\cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires loss in wt., 6.56%.)

This hexahydrated salt is also obtained when a solution of the heptahydrated zinc hydroxyfluoberyllate is allowed to crystallise on a water-bath. The other hydrated salts could not be isolated. In the case of the sulphate also, the penta-, tetra- and tri-hydrated salts, if they exist at all, are not stable under the ordinary conditions. When the hexahydrated zinc hydroxyfluoberyllate is heated to a constant weight nearly at 200° , the monohydrated salt is formed. (Found : Loss in wt., 39.99%. $\text{ZnBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires loss in wt., 39.3%). The monohydrated salt is appreciably less soluble than the two other hydrated salts.

Cadmium hydroxyfluoberyllate 8/3 hydrate was prepared by the first as well as by the second method. This substance is very hygroscopic and highly soluble in water and in 60% alcohol. (Found : Cd, 45.97 ; F, 23.39. $\text{CdBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot 8/3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cd, 46.15 ; F, 23.41 per cent).

Manganese hydroxyfluoberyllate tetrahydrate is interesting because the magnesium fluoberyllates have not yet been isolated. This salt was prepared by the second method. (Found : Mn, 25.99 ; F, 26.88 ; Be, 4.11. $\text{MnBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Mn, 26.16 ; F 27.14 ; Be, 4.29 per cent).

This salt is also highly soluble in water and is slightly deliquescent. When heated to a constant weight at 85° , it was found to change into the monohydrated salt. (Found : F, 36.52. $\text{MnBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires F, 36.55 per cent).

Ferrous hydroxyfluoberyllate heptahydrate was prepared by the first method. Iron in ferrous hydroxyfluoberyllate shows a marked tendency for absorbing oxygen from air and to change into the ferric state. During the preparation of this compound a few scraps of reduced iron were therefore taken in the platinum basin. The hydrogen liberated by the action of the acid on the metal prevented the oxidation. Alternatively, the reaction may be carried out in an inert atmosphere. The reaction between the ferrous nitrite and ammonium hydroxyfluoberyllate affords a mixture of basic salts, ferrous hydroxyfluoberyllate and possibly ferric hydroxyfluoberyllate. (Found : F, 21.72 ; Fe, 20.68 ; Be, 3.19. $\text{FeBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires F, 21.51 ; Fe, 21.12 ; Be, 3.40 per cent).

Ferrous hydroxyfluoberyllate is almost colorless, and when kept over sulphuric acid in a desiccator it loses nearly three molecules of water, yielding the tetrahydrated salt.

Cobalt hydroxyfluoberyllate heptahydrate was prepared by the first and the third methods. The solution was allowed to crystallise in a refrigerator. (Found : Co, 21.61 ; F, 21.00 ; Be, 3.27. $\text{CoBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Co, 21.85 ; F, 21.26 ; Be, 3.36 per cent).

When the solution was allowed to crystallise on the water-bath, the hexahydrated compound was obtained. (Found : F, 22.67. $\text{CoBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires F, 22.80 per cent).

The rose-red crystals are converted into the trihydrated salt when kept in a vacuum desiccator over sulphuric acid. (Found : Loss in wt., 21.40%. $\text{CoBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot 3 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires loss in wt., 21.62%).

On heating the hexahydrated salt to a constant weight at 80°, the dihydrated salt was obtained as a dusty red powder. (Found: Loss in wt., 29.73%. $\text{CoBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot 2 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires loss in wt., 28.82%).

The cobaltic hydroxyfluoberyllate could not be prepared but its amines have been isolated:

Nickel Hydroxyfluoberyllate Heptahydrate.—When the solution obtained by the first method was allowed to crystallise at a temperature below 20°, beautiful green monoclinic crystals of nickel hydroxyfluoberyllate heptahydrate were obtained. (Found: Ni, 21.70; F, 21.23; Be, 3.32. $\text{NiBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot 7 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 21.92; F, 21.28; Be, 3.37 per cent).

If during the process of crystallisation the temperature of the solution goes above 30°, the hexahydrated salt is obtained. (Found: Ni, 23.32; F, 22.68; Be, 3.58. $\text{NiBeF}_3\text{OH} \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Ni, 23.49; F, 22.82; Be, 3.61 per cent).

The hydroxyfluoberyllate of nickel is highly soluble in water. At 30° 100 c. c. of the saturated solution contains 39.5 g. of nickel fluoberyllate, while the same amount of a saturated solution of nickel hydroxyfluoberyllate at the same temperature contains 69.8 g. of nickel hydroxyfluoberyllate.

The other hydrated salts of nickel hydroxyfluoberyllate could not be isolated. In the case of sulphate also, the penta-, tetra-, tri- and di-hydrated salts are metastable (Chretien and Rohmer, *Compt. rend.*, 1934, 193, 92). The crystalline overgrowth of the nickel hydroxyfluoberyllate on a crystal of nickel sulphate was observed. These two salts are therefore isomorphous. Similar observation has already been made in connection with the potassium and barium salts by X-ray analysis.

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